

Changes in the economic importance of rice insect pests in Vietnam.

Insect	Economic importance ^a	
	1956-68	1969-81
<i>Cnaphalocrocis medinalis</i> (Guenée)	–	XXX
<i>Tetroda histeroideis</i> Fabricius	–	XX
<i>Baliothrips bififormis</i> (Bagnall)	–	X
<i>Nilaparvata lugens</i> (Stål)	X	XXX
<i>Mythimna unipuncta</i> (Haw.)	XXX	XXX
<i>Orseolia oryzae</i> (Wood-Mason)	XX	XX
<i>Chilo suppressalis</i> (Walker)	XXX	XX
<i>Scirpophaga incertulas</i> (Walker)	XXX	XX
<i>Sesamia inferens</i> (Walker)	XXX	XX
<i>Gryllotalpa africana</i> (P. de B.)	X	X
<i>Sogatella furcifera</i> (Horvath)	X	X
<i>Leptocorisa acuta</i> (Thunberg)	X	X
<i>Nymphula depunctalis</i> (Guenee)	X	X
<i>Chlorops oryzae</i> (Mats.)	X	X
<i>Nephotettix nigropictus</i> (Stål)	X	–
<i>Nephotettix virescens</i> (Distant)	X	–
<i>Scotinophora lurida</i> Burmeister	X	–
<i>Parnara guttata</i> (Bremer & Grey)	XXX	–
<i>Pelopidas mathias</i> (Fabr.)	XXX	–
<i>Spodoptera mauritia</i> (Boisb.)	XXX	–
<i>Dicladisia armigera</i> (Olivier)	XXX	–

^axxx = causing severe damage every year; xx = causing extensive damage in some areas every year; x = causing heavy damage under certain conditions; – = negligible damage.

Nilaparvata lugens, a minor problem during the 1960s, has become increasingly prevalent during the 1970s in sev-

eral rice-growing areas. *Cnaphalocrocis medinalis* shows a similar change.

But *Spodoptera mauritia*, *Parnara*

guttata, *Pelopidas mathias*, and *Dicladisia armigera*, defined as major insect pests in the 1960s, are minor pests now.

Incidence of some insects has increased in certain areas of the country during critical times of the growing season. *Chilo suppressalis*, *Scirpophaga incertulas*, and *Sesamia inferens* are problems in the Red River Delta. *C. suppressalis* causes extensive damage in the dry season, *S. incertulas* in the wet season, and *S. inferens* in both seasons.

Mythimna unipuncta causes serious damage during the preharvest stage in the wet season in the northern provinces. *Orseolia oryzae* is more dominant during seedling and tillering stages in the dry season in the central provinces. *Leptocorisa acuta*, *Tetroda histeroideis*, *Scotinophora lurida*, and *Baliothrips bififormis* occasionally cause extensive damage in some locations. ■

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Deep water

Yellow rice borer incidence in deepwater rice in Thailand, 1981

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Rice borer damage was surveyed in 63 deepwater rice fields distributed over the Central Plains of Thailand. The survey from flood inundation to harvest included 24 farmer-named rice varieties, mostly floating types.

The yellow rice borer *Scirpophaga incertulas* (Walker) comprised more than 95% of the borer population in rice stems dissected. The number of damaged stems increased from 3% at the early elongation stage to 37% at harvest (see figure). An exceptionally high 71% damaged stems at the ripening stage was recorded for 3 fields of Leb Mue Nahng

Average incidence of stems damaged by rice borer, predominantly the yellow rice borer *Scirpophaga incertulas*, in deepwater rice fields. Thailand, 1981.

111 at Prachin Buri.

At an outbreak threshold of 20% damaged stems, 67% of the fields were at outbreak level in the booting and

heading stage and 89% were at harvest. Counts in 35 fields at harvest showed 2.5% whiteheads, a ratio of 1 whitehead to 15 damaged stems. ■